

REINCARNATE

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Dear **changemaker**,

In this new edition, we're excited to bring you the latest updates in **our mission to enable a circular built environment**. From a successful General Assembly in Cologne to hands-on pilot visits, new training opportunities, workshops, and scientific publications, [Reincarnate](#) continues to drive change through innovation, collaboration, and knowledge sharing. We invite you to explore these highlights and join us in shaping the future of construction.

Enjoy your reading!

PROJECT UPDATES

General Assembly in Cologne

On March 13-14, the [Reincarnate](#) consortium gathered in Cologne, hosted by our partner [3L Architects](#), to assess progress, refine strategies, and define the steps for the final phase of the project.

What we tackled:

- ✓ Real-world demonstrations of circular innovations – from BIM-based tools to AI-driven material valuation
- ✓ Capacity building through interactive workshops & training platform updates
- ✓ Strengthening exploitation pathways & industry alignment
- ✓ Growing impact through dissemination & standardization efforts.

[Find out more](#)

Reincarnate Innovations – The Full Toolbox for Circular Construction

In the construction industry, innovation plays a crucial role in addressing sustainability challenges. As part of the Reincarnate project, **ten groundbreaking innovations** are being developed to advance circular construction practices. The **Innovation Series videos** highlight these pioneering solutions and the experts behind them describing the innovation, the specific challenges in construction and demolition (C&D) it aims to solve, the inspiration behind it, and the stage of development.

The video thumbnail features the 'REINCARNATE INNOVATIONS' logo on the left, which includes a circular arrow icon. The title 'Interfaces to existing data and planning tools' is displayed in white and green text. Below the title, the speaker's name 'Samaneh Rezvani' and her role 'Senior Researcher & Head of the Research Unit at DEMO Consultants' are listed. A red play button icon is centered over the text. On the right side, there is a circular portrait of Samaneh Rezvani. At the bottom right, the European Union flag logo is accompanied by the text 'Funded by the European Union'.

[Check our innovation videos](#)

[Visiting the Lagemaat Pilot to Explore How Reincarnate Innovations Can Optimize Construction Processes](#)

On Feb. 7th, the Reincarnate team had the privilege of visiting [Lagemaat Sloopwerken B.V.](#), one of our pilot partners in the Netherlands. As a progressive "remolition" company, Lagemaat is at the forefront of **sustainable deconstruction**.

They actively practice "LEGOLiseren" – treating old buildings as donor structures, carefully dismantling prefabconcrete elements, and repurposing them for new, modern constructions.

At Reincarnate, we are exploring how our innovations can further optimize Lagemaat's processes, making circular construction even more efficient and impactful.

[Discover more about our visit](#)

Introducing the Reincarnate Academy: Innovation and Upskilling for All

We are excited to have launched the Reincarnate Academy - a platform designed to make digital innovations accessible and provide targeted training for stakeholders in the construction industry.

[Register today and start your learning journey!](#)

SCIENCE AND RESEARCH

New Publications

Leveraging AI to Create a Circular Built Environment

Published in Amplify (Vol. 37, No. 11), this article by TU Delft researchers explores the **innovative use of AI to drive sustainable practices in the built environment**, aligning with the goals of Reincarnate, which focuses on reducing construction and demolition waste while fostering circular economy principles.

[Read the publication](#)

Towards Desirable Futures for the Circular Adaptive Reuse of Buildings: A Participatory Approach

Published in Sustainable Cities and Society (Vol. 122, 106259), the paper **explores the complexities and opportunities of adaptive reuse in the context of circular economy principles**. It underscores how repurposing existing structures – rather than building new ones – can significantly reduce waste, conserve resources, and lower CO2 emissions.

[Read the publication](#)

INNOVATIVE INSIGHTS

2 Discussion Forums & 2 Workshops

Discussion Forums

#1 Adopting Circular Innovation Tools in the Construction Industry

This webinar - featuring insights from [Ragn-Sells](#), [3L](#), and [Erasmus University Rotterdam](#), explored how circular business models can turn waste into valuable resources and why scaling them remains a challenge. It showed that waste requires proper data to become usable material, secondary raw materials need stronger policy support, and shifting mindsets through communication is just as important as technical innovation.

#2: Creating Public Value Through Circular Waste Reduction in Construction

Experts from [MadaStar](#), [TU Delft](#), and [University of Twente](#) explored how to advance circular construction while ensuring long-term public value. They emphasized that material tracking is essential for reuse, decision-making frameworks help sustain sustainability goals, buildings should be treated as material banks, and aligning circularity with public priorities remains a key challenge.

[Learn more](#)

[Learn more](#)

Workshops

Developing Guidelines to Overcome Barriers in Adopting Reincarnate 10 Innovations

On February 6, 2025, Reincarnate hosted a collaborative workshop at [Erasmus University Rotterdam \(EUR\)](#) in partnership with [Technische Universität Berlin \(TUB\)](#).

The focus of the meeting was to collaboratively develop guidelines that will help overcome barriers in adopting circular innovations in construction materials and products.

[Read more](#)

Insights from Reincarnate Value Planning Workshop

A value planning session hosted by [DEMO Consultants](#) and led by [Ragn-Sells](#) focused on refining on understanding how data is structured and connected within the platform, identifying gaps, and outlining necessary improvements.

Key discussions addressed challenges in data integration and system compatibility, shaping the next steps for refining processes and ensuring a more efficient workflow.

[Read more](#)

REINCARNATE AROUND EUROPE

Reincarnate partners participated in recent events across Europe, sharing insights and solutions for advancing circular construction.

At [DIGICON 2024](#) in Munich, Sabine Kruschwitz (TU Berlin) presented Reincarnate's SLAMD tool and its role in developing sustainable building materials. We're proud to share that SLAMD earned third place in DIGICON's prestigious Innovation Award competition,

showcasing its potential to revolutionize construction practices by reducing environmental impacts and improving resource efficiency.

At the **[Construction Summit 2025](#)** in Stockholm, our partner [Ragn-Sells](#) joined industry stakeholders to discuss circular material flows, digital traceability, and collaboration across the value chain.

[Mostostal Warszawa](#) gave a [guest lecture on BIM](#) and circular construction at the **Warsaw University of Life Sciences**, Faculty of Civil Engineering, showcasing Reincarnate's work on digital workflows and sustainable planning

[Find out more](#)

Follow us and stay tuned!

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